

Blockbuster vs Netflix

Families have always used their free time to share entertainment activities outside and inside their homes. Activity patterns that meet those needs respond to preferences and customs rooted in different cultures and contexts. In the most recent years, a new technological change is presented which is the development of the internet, which has allowed the transmission of information and data extremely fast and with high volumes of information. For many years, Blockbuster was the dominant company in the video rental brick and mortar business. When Netflix appeared in the scene, with the strategy of sending DVDs by mail, they offered consumers in the United States a cheaper, faster, and more convenient way to “rent” the movies via streaming, which resulted in Blockbuster disappearing from the market. Netflix took advantage of the advances in technology, and made a significant diversification of products by offering customers the possibility to watch movies, series and programs with the simple touch of a button. When you think of movies at home or on mobile devices, Netflix is the brand that has managed to position itself as the most recognized alternative in the market. The success of Netflix is not given freely, but is the result of correct decisions, crossings of variables, analysis and astuteness to enter the market. For these reasons and many more, we can say that Netflix has content marketing lessons to offer.

Blockbuster

The main cause of the failure that led to bankruptcy of Blockbuster was a clear lack of vision and adaptation to the future, and its leaders were not able to make the necessary changes to a market

that was moving and the decision to acquire companies to continue growing. The company did not realize that they had this competition of downloads or streaming over the internet that started to grow rapidly, thus making them pointless because they were not taking any measures to improve. They did not take awareness that the physical format of DVDs and Blu Ray were no longer profitable like cable television or the different internet platforms.

Netflix

Netflix extracts information to analyze and understand current and potential subscribers; therefore, they can develop successful marketing and advertising campaigns. In addition, it analyzes the information that the subscriber provides: name, email address, address, payment method and telephone. It also analyzes the information collected automatically: movie selections, searches, interactions and use of the Netflix service. They have 16 effective ways of advertising, applications, and websites. They also possess different tools, great customer service, as well as information about the computer or other devices used to access Netflix.

KPI's to analysis competition

- Financial
- Marketing and sales
- Innovation
- Human Resources

SWOT

Blockbuster

Strengths

Retail Outlet Network
Access to new movies before Netflix
Strong brand recognition

Opportunities

Alliances with other companies (Facebook, Google)
Rental kiosks
Dish Networks

Weakness

Poor streaming presence
Poor online platform

Threats

Netflix
Amazon
Comcast
Hulu

Netflix

Strengths

Personalization
Technology
Original Content
Reasonable Prices

Opportunities

Partnerships
Content for all the public

Weakness

Movies after 2 years they came out
Depends on internet connection
The content varies in every country

Threats

New competitors(Disney, Apple, etc)
Piracy